

Institute *of* **Physics**

**Environmental
Physics Group**

Newsletter

October 2000

Editor's Report

The bulk of this Newsletter is devoted to the 10th Anniversary Meeting of the Environmental Physics Group, held on 17 May 2000 at the Institute of Physics Headquarters, and attended by 40 members of the group and guests. It was a very stimulating meeting which fully demonstrated our theme, *The Diversity of Environmental Physics*.

There is also a report of the talk, given by Dr. John Swanson of the National Grid on 7 June 2000, on the important topic of whether electromagnetic fields cause cancer and how physicists might help to find out.

Finally, may I draw your attention to some forthcoming meetings, especially the Third International Conference on Urban Air Quality in Greece in March 2001. Some travel bursaries are available to members of the EPG, especially postgraduate students. As indicated in the April Newsletter, applications for these grants should be made by letter or email to Peter Hodgson at least one month before the meeting date. The EPG is also combining with the Medical Physics Group to mount a one-day meeting on *Physical Environment and Health* at Physics Congress 2001 in Brighton.

Derek Rose

ENVIRONMENTAL PHYSICS GROUP

9th ANNUAL GENERAL MEETING

London, 17th May 2000

MINUTES

The assembled members were welcomed to the AGM by the Chairman, Professor Edward Youngs, who proceeded to present his report for the year (see elsewhere in this issue). This was followed by a report given by the Honorary Secretary, which included a financial statement (also see in this issue). Further breakdown of the expenditure through the year was presented at the AGM. Although there exists a vacancy on the Committee, there were no nominations and therefore no elections were held.

The AGM concluded with a brief discussion, which covered topics including finance and communication between the membership.

Financial Summary 1999-2000

1999 Finances

Balance b/fwd	£456.47
1999 Budget award	£4,554.00
Expenditure	(£2,672.92)
Balance c/fwd	£2,337.55

2000 Finances

Balance b/fwd	£2,337.55
2000 Budget award	£4,578.00
Expenditure to 31/3/99	(£371.18)
Balance @ 31/3/99	£6,544.37

Secretary & Treasurer's Report

I must start by thanking Edward Youngs for his great efforts in organising the Member's Day / 10th Anniversary Meeting and also Peter Hughes who had the original idea to celebrate the Group's founding in this way. Although there are challenges in running a Group as diverse as ours, I think we can look forward very positively to the next 10 years.

There are no elections to the Committee at this year's AGM, although there is one vacancy on the Committee. Any enthusiastic volunteers should make themselves known to me as soon as possible.

A few facts and figures; this year Group membership stands at 552, up from 509 last year. The increase is roughly in line with the increase in IoP membership. The Group finances are in good shape, mainly as a result of the increased central funding for Groups. We do have better financial resources than in the past and I would like to put these to the best possible use in enabling and supporting Group activities and in assisting more members of the Group to become *active* members of the Group. One result of the improving financial situation is the Travel Bursary scheme, which is now up and running. Aimed at, but not limited to, students and post-doctoral researchers, I would ask you to publicise the scheme to your colleagues in the Group.

One other item the committee has been looking at that I would like to highlight, is the database of Member's interests. This is being set up so that the committee can go to the right people within the Group when we get requests for expert opinion and so that we can target Group activities to suit the membership.

Communication is vital for the well-being of the Group and I intend to make increasing use of the email facilities being set-up by the IoP to disseminate information about events. Please keep your email and other contact details up to date on the annual subscription renewal form to ensure messages get through. The Newsletter and the Group Web pages are also undergoing change and I would encourage members to use and contribute to both. We are also looking at the possibility of running a Web-based Environmental Physics Bulletin Board. Comments about the likely up-take of this would be welcome.

Finally my thanks go to the Committee for their efforts this year and in particular to Edward Youngs, who has put in a great deal of effort and commitment to maintain the success of the Group.

Peter Hodgson

May 2000

Environmental Physics Group -Chairman' Report -- 17 May 2000

In its tenth year of existence, the Environmental Physics Group has a membership of about 500. Because of the wide spread of interests of members, combined meetings with other groups and organisations have been the main activity of the Group and will continue to be in the future. Thus, last year our Annual General Meeting in May was followed by a well-attended talk by Jon Shanklin on work in the Antarctic concerned with the Ozone hole, held jointly with the London and South East Branch of the Institute of Physics; and we joined with the Combustion Group at the Physics' Congress in Brighton in March this year in a symposium with very good speakers on the Environmental Consequences of Combustion that was attended by about 50 delegates. In July the Group co-sponsored a meeting on Optical Oceanography and UV Radiation during the 22nd General Assembly of the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics at the University of Birmingham, and in September we helped with the session on Global Environmental Change at the British Association meeting in Sheffield.

Meetings planned for this year start on 7 June with a talk by John Swanson who will examine the much-publicised suggestion of a link between electromagnetic fields and human health. This meeting will be jointly held again with the London and South East Branch. Another meeting planned is a meeting on bioaerosols, which will include the consideration of the environment associated with agricultural crops. The Third International Conference on Urban Air Quality, which the Group will again co-sponsor, will be held in Loutraki in Greece on 19-23 March 2001.

The committee has been asked on a number of occasions to help the Institute in formulating submissions on Government Department reports. It is felt that members often have the expertise to comment better on these reports than the committee itself. In order to obtain a greater awareness of the expertise of members who could help on these matters, and also for the committee to cater better for the wide interests of the Group and perhaps swell the numbers at events, a questionnaire, intended to extend the Institute's database, has recently been sent out to members.

Members will have noted with pleasure that the Institute of Physics Charles Chree Award and Medal now includes specifically "environmental physics" in its citation, and they should note that the Institute welcomes nominations for its awards from individual members when the Institute asks for nominations in future.

We have to thank Barbara Gabrys for her work in setting up the WEB page for the Group. We are also setting up a Bulletin Board for members, and more on this will be announced in due course. As regards the Newsletter, there have been difficulties during the change of editors. The new editor, Derek Rose, hopes to be able to produce at regular intervals a Newsletter of a slimmer nature than we had with the last editors. I would encourage members to supply material both for our Web page and the Newsletter, and also to communicate their thoughts and ideas for events to committee members.

Lastly, I have to thank on your behalf the work of the committee members and in particular our Secretary, Peter Hodgson. We now look forward to a further ten years for the Environmental Physics Group, during which time environmental physics will have more and more an important role to play in every day life.

E.G. Youngs

THE DIVERSITY OF ENVIRONMENTAL PHYSICS

Tenth Anniversary Meeting 17 May 2000

The meeting comprised a full day of talks and discussion supported by posters and a photographic exhibition, all of which combined to illustrate the diversity of our subject.

After an introduction from the Chairman of the EPG, Dr. E.G. Youngs, the first speaker was A.E. Mill (Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory, Birkenhead) who gave an overview of the physics of shallow seas, demonstrating how temperature, salinity and gravity combine to induce many of the flows and mixing phenomena observed in shallow seas around the world. Next, I. Colbeck (University of Essex) convincingly demonstrated that air pollution knows no boundaries; he was followed by D. Pearson (University of Reading) who gave an overview of progress in using passive microwave remote sensing to monitor the hydrological state of soils. After lunch, J. Saffell (Alphasense Ltd., Dunmow) outlined how emerging technologies can advance analyses of gaseous and VOC emissions. This was followed by an idiosyncratic and controversial contribution by R.T. Jarman (ex CEEB Portishead) on how some of the consequences of the greenhouse effect might be mitigated, leading to a lively discussion in which his ideas were seriously challenged.

After tea there were two contributions. A. Cripps (Buro Happold, London) described the fascinating environmental physics of the Millennium Dome, especially the problems of ventilation and of crowd movement towards the exits in emergencies. Finally, H.A. McCartney (Rothamsted Experimental Station) gave an overview of how environmental physics is used in crop protection.

There were several posters. Mhaari Coyle (ITE, Edinburgh) demonstrated the use of micrometeorology to measure and model ozone fluxes to vegetation in Britain. Mike Koefman (Manchester) made the case for a hydrogen economy to fuel the 21st century. Barbara Gabrys and Mike Tilley (Open University, Oxford) outlined the forces behind electrical vehicles. Alexandra Wilson (Ove Arup and Partners, London) illustrated several aspects of the environmental work of a consulting engineering company, including condensation analysis, CFD modelling of water flows, shade visualization, prediction of internal space conditions, assessment of façade performance, 2D heat transfer through elements of building façades, ray tracing, and predictions of thermal comfort. D.D. Macneil and colleagues (CEH, Wallingford) described the construction and performance of HYDRA - an automated integrated system for measuring vertical gas fluxes by eddy correlation.

Finally, there was a display of 16 photographs, most of them taken by Peter Hughes, recording some of the personalities, activities, locations and instrumentation involved in environmental physics, which demonstrated the scope and breadth of our subject area.

Derek Rose

Do Electromagnetic Fields Cause Cancer And How Can Physicists Help To Find Out?

The idea that a link exists between electric power lines and illnesses, in particular childhood leukemia, has been debated in the media for over twenty years. More recently, the increase in use of mobile phones has caused yet more public concern. A talk by John Swanson, of the National Grid Company, at the IoP on the 7 June 2000, aimed to address some of the questions that the public have about EM fields and to offer some opinions on how physicists can aid the issue by trying to uncover how EM fields could affect biological systems. After an introduction on the sizes of field required to cause effects in cells and people, the talk moved on to how the possibility of a link between the low level fields the public is normally exposed to and cancer could be investigated.

Epidemiology was the first such method discussed, whereby human populations are studied to see if there is a pattern between the incidence of a disease and its suspected cause, in this case power lines. Such studies have been contradictory, although the majority of more recent work found no link between a person's proximity to a power line and their development of disease, particularly cancer. The second method, of directly subjecting cell cultures or animals to EM fields, has proved inconclusive. Of the biological studies completed on exposure to sub- μ T magnetic fields, none have been reproducible. So far then, biological testing has not been helpful in evaluating whether a link exists between EM fields and cancer.

The third method was the one most relevant to physicists; is there a mechanism by which EM fields could cause cancer? More specifically, is there a way in which an EM field can produce an effect at molecular level that is plausible and does it produce an effect on an individual molecule or cell that is in any case greater than that produced by noise at the molecular or cell level? Various mechanisms were discussed over the course of the talk. Most methods (induction of currents in cells, oscillation of magnetite in the brain with field ...) were judged unlikely to cause disease on the basis that the effects that they would cause were less than the noise level generally present in the body. More recent theories, that it is not the direct effect of a magnetic field on the body but the indirect effect of the electric field of the power lines changing in some way the properties of the surrounding air, at first seemed more plausible. However, when such effects were studied in more detail, it was found that people had to be very close to the power line for any effect to become noticeable (less than 20 m and outdoors for one theory, closer than 1 m for another).

The answer to the question "do power lines cause cancer?" therefore had to be no, the balance of evidence accumulated over twenty years is against this. However, the speaker pointed out, it could never be guaranteed that they do not.

A small section at the end of the talk dealt with the issue of mobile phones. Here the fact that research into the effects of mobile phones has gone on for less than five years means that the question is left very much open to debate. The talk ended with the comforting notion that "the world needs physicists" and with questions from the audience which covered all aspects of the talk.

Karen Yates, Imperial College, London

Forthcoming Meetings

The Third International Conference on Urban Air Quality

Measurement, Modelling and Management

19 - 23 March 2001

The Poseidon Hotel Resort

Loutraki, Greece

Introduction

This conference is the third in a series which began with the highly successful meeting at the University of Hertfordshire, United Kingdom in July 1996 followed by the equally successful second conference, held at the Technical University of Madrid, March 1999. The overall aim of this meeting is to provide a forum for scientists, engineers and decision and policy makers to meet and discuss the latest developments in urban air quality. It is hoped that this series of conferences will encourage international collaboration between researchers with the purpose of collectively advancing the frontiers of this challenging and exciting field. In light of this, the organisers welcome the participation of COST 715, SATURN and TRAPOS which all represent important international frameworks for urban air pollution research.

Venue

The conference will take place at the Poseidon Hotel Resort, 2.5 km from the town of Loutraki, Greece. Located on the eastern corner of the Corinthian gulf, the seaside hotel is surrounded by archaeological sites and places of historical interest.

Conference topics

The topics of the conference will include:

- Measurement and monitoring of urban air pollutants on a local and urban scale
- Sampling techniques and instrumentation
- Measurement of urban meteorological parameters
- Transformation and dispersion processes
- Emission models and inventories
- Source apportionment studies

- Local and Urban scale modelling
- Early warning systems and forecast modelling
- Roadside air quality modelling including street canyons
- Wind tunnel & physical modelling studies
- Modelling evaluation and sensitivity studies
- Use of remote sensing and satellite data assimilation for urban air quality
- Personal exposure and environmental and health impact of urban air pollution
- Urban air quality management systems (AQMS) and decision support systems (DSS)
- Urban air quality databases, information systems and data archiving

Abstract Submission

Abstracts of 300 words (no figures) should be submitted by **Friday 1 September 2000** using one of the following methods:

Internet: Full online submission of your personal details, abstract text, references and figures is available via the conference website at:
<http://www.iop.org/IOP/Confs/UAQ>

Enquiries and Information

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Supported by AWMA, IUAPPA and EURASAP

6th International Conference on Optical Particle Characterisation

2 - 5 April 2001

The Old Ship Hotel, Brighton, UK

Brochures for this meeting have already been circulated, but full details are available via the conference website at:

<http://www.iop.org/IOP/Confs/OPC>

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